

ACTIVATION OF INFORMATION FRAGMENTS IN THE TEXT

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Abstract: This article deals with activation of information fragments in the text. It also analyzes the possibilities of informational expression of speech structures that act as a complex unit of meaning in the structure of the text, the participation of the principle of linguistic austerity in determining the information scale.

Key words: economy of speech, ellipsis, interpretation, description of the text phenomenon, economy of mental effort, speech structures, a unit of

A functional communicative approach to the study of the language system favors the analysis of the patterns of their movement in speech communication situations rather than the stagnant state of language units. This approach takes into account all the conditions of communication, including the stock of linguistic and non-linguistic knowledge of the speakers and listeners. Against this background, not simple language units (words, word combinations, vs. sentences) are chosen as units of analysis, but structures that represent information in full and texts that are formed with their participation.

In the second half of the last century, the traditional belief that "the greatest unity of linguistic analysis is speech", which has long been emphasized, was put to an end and began to be recognized as the main means of communication, a separate semiotic phenomenon - text. During this period, the question of determining the structure of the text and what constitutes its content came to the attention of linguists. And in subsequent years, the development of textual linguistics has reached the next level, and researchers are consistently studying the semantic, stylistic and pragmatic characteristics of the text.

Russian scientist on Stylistics I.R.Galperin's description of the text phenomenon has been repeated in many works. According to the scientist, the text is a literary formed speech work with a meaningful integrity. We are also in favor of interpreting the text as an informational complex consisting of a set of data of different levels.

According to this interpretation, the text, as a unit of communication, embodies a certain picture of the universe or an extralinguistic situation. But in the text, the part of the situation that is considered important by the speaker is expressed directly. The reflection of this situation in the text constitutes its content, and

information about the situation takes place from this content. The set of information that an expression finds in the text consists of parts, fragments that reflect various microsituations, and on the basis of the interaction of these fragments, the text takes on a holistic view.

Scientist of Translation study, A.Chernyakhovskaya developed a method for separating these information units . The essence of this method is as follows. At first, the information complex that forms the content of the text is considered as a hierarchic structure consisting of three stages. The lower stage of these steps is occupied by elementary (primitive) content units. Such units are small fragments of information, and the linguistic means that represent them express a fragment of reality. The elementary content unit being allocated, in turn, will consist of four parts: 1) information about the subject, the name of the event; 2) information about the time and space in which the event is taking place; 3) Information representing the modality; 4) meaning of existence. The meaning of existence is expressed in the text as a linguistic unit of a certain type, that is, a predicate structure.

The predicate structure is the sum of linguistic signs that evoke fragments of meaning that are mentioned in the mind of the listener (reader). Importantly, some of these meanings may not even find a transparent expression. In addition to the fact that the predicate structure has the appearance of a structurally simple sentence, a word combination, it may not be in the form of a linguistic sign.

Elementary units of meaning combine among themselves to form complex units of meaning. Information about the object being named also takes place from the composition of such units. Hence, the structure that forms as a result of the accumulation of various units of meaning can be called text. Since a complex content structure reflects a certain reality, situation, the continuity of all information fragments is considered as a criterion for its differentiation, the change of any fragment testifies to the presence of a border between speech structures.

Thus, we will try to analyze the possibilities of informational expression of speech structures that act as a complex unit of meaning in the structure of the text. In this case, the main attention is paid to determining the participation of the principle of linguistic austerity in determining the information scale.

It is customary to study the dialogue that goes between the characters of works of art as a separate manifestation of oral speech . Because in the written formation of the text of oral speech, its main linguistic and methodological features are preserved. But it is also observed that in a literary text some elements

characteristic of verbal communication are omitted. Due to the fact that the dialogue is constantly associated with a certain reality, situation, the elements saved by the form is logically restored through the analysis of the same situation. In order to achieve a complete restoration of missing components, one sometimes has to resort to the full text of a work of art.

First of all, it is necessary to consider cases of transparent expression of information components in the analyzed speech structures. The observations made testify to the fact that in the syntactic structure of structures, information carrier units of meaning do not exist uniformly. The number of informational components found by the expression of the expression is different: sometimes it can also be one.

To facilitate the description of the collected material, we use the following gestures: e – information about existence; m – modal fragment; t – Time Indicator; s - space indicator; b – property; a – a subject with these signs. It is worth mentioning that the modal component of the speech structure is characterized from the point of view of the content of the objective and subjective modality. I.R.Galperin believes that "the inclusion of the subjective modality in the general modality category is an important stage in expanding the scale of the grammatical analysis of the sentence, and in this way a bridge is thrown from the sentence to the analysis of the text."

Uzbek scientist S.Boymirzaeva, reflecting on the possibilities of expression of the text modality, notes that any type of modality, including the subjective modality, is associated with the relativity of knowledge about the universe. "Event in the universe in the process of studying phenomena by analogy, we come to approximate, probable conclusions. Accordingly, at the center of the field of subjective modality, which is the result of gnoseological activity, is probably the meaning of Assumption."

Based on the above points, we found that in order to study the information scale of the speech structures of the objective modality, it is necessary to first take into account the expression of the objective modality. The subjective modality, on the other hand, signals additional information expression.

We will analyze the following example, taken from D.Salinger's "A Perfect Day for Banana Fish":

...but the brother said: "I'd better test your eyes again while you're here, just to make seem" (D.Salinger. A Perfect Day for Banana Fish).

In this passage, the part you're here is being allocated as a structure with a separate informational content. Because in its composition anaphoric exchange

(you instead of I) occurs, the word goes about another person. Also, the morphological form of the modality is changing: instead of the optative, declarative mood is activated.

In this speech structure, all informational components are expressed explicitly: the subject performing the action – you (used in place of the name Joan); Sema of existence (e) to be expressed in the means of the verb; modality (m) – realized in the means of the verb form; meaning of the tense (t) – took the form of Present Indefinite.

In the speech structure, which is highlighted in the following fragment of the dialogue, all the information fragments are linguistically realised:

“He was remarkable kind”.

“Kind?”

“Oh, yes, in the circumstances. Because she started up a lot of gossip in the neighborhood”. (D.Salinger. A Perfect Day for Banana Fish).

This colloquial structure is part of an adverb, and the reason why it is considered as a separate colloquial unit is explained by the presence in it of more than one predicate phrase. Also in its composition, instead of the element he in the previous sentence, the pronoun she appears. This pronoun serves as the seat of the name Miss Simonds. The content of the element in the neighborhood is understood from the context and realities the sema of space. When the verb form Started informs about the participation of two subjects, the mood form of this verb expresses the meaning of the modality. The tense index finds expression in the medium of the form of Past Indefinite.

In most speech structures, the component pointing to space goes under the principle of economy. In general, the presence of a locative fragment from a syntactic structure is not a regular indicator for dialogical speech. After all, dialogical communication occurs mainly at the address of the situation being described, or this address is known to the participants in the dialogue. The taking of a linguistic form of a locative element is due to the fact that the statement goes beyond the speech situation or is associated with the goal of a thematic interpretation.

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